

Political Leaning Over Public Interests: A Discourse Analysis

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ABSTRACT

This descriptive analysis is conducted to empirically investigate the agenda-setting role of corporate news media in Pakistan. Five cardinal private television news channels are selected as the sample of the study and responses are documented during 9 p.m. news bulletin being broadcasted on them. Agenda-setting theory of mass media provides a conceptual background to this research project. The cross-tabulation method is used to manipulate the obtained frequencies of responses. Thus, it is found that national political news reports are being given analogously more exposure than other national and international concerns. Similarly, reports addressing the common man, encouraging public participation and welfare are not being given enough exposure. Therefore, it is suggested that corporate news media should consider the wellbeing of the common man and public welfare should be the first priority of media reporting which is the main ethical prerequisite of journalism practices.

Keywords: News media; Public interest; Discourse Analysis; Agenda-Setting; Framing; Local Political New

1. INTRODUCTION

Agenda setting is one of the core conceptual frameworks in mass media research. Especially, news media illustrates this function at large. Media has always been under critical allegations regarding focusing on some particular issues and, neglecting the others. Especially, political scenarios are being more focused as compared to that of the common man which, in turn, leads to negligence towards public matters. Walgrave & Aelst, (2016, p. 1) stated that giving coverage to political issues have potential effects on diverting the audience's attention according to the media agenda. It mainly depends upon the "Political actor" who have a greater tendency to persuade a target audience. Mediatized politics is directly affected by strategies being used for political communication. Through agenda setting practice, media determine which issue should be given more consideration and ultimately, which problems meet policy solution (Thesen, p. 7). Agenda setting role of media has a potential influence to alter public agendas by directly placing media agendas on public opinion. McCombs, (2011, p. 17) stated that pictures about the outside world are continuously affected by mass media about, what and

how to perceive them? Thus, agenda setting in mass media has significant impacts on reshaping public opinion. In this case, analysing role of news media regarding its main focus on political and international issues by neglecting other social issues is of greater importance. The mass media effects, (Mccombs, 2013) the very pictures of the world in our minds. While describing the agenda-setting role of media, it is imperative to analyse factors that are the reasons behind setting the agenda and their subsequent influences on opinions and, behaviours. There is a number of national, international and local news being covered by news media worldwide. Media hegemony and political economy, in this case, are said to be responsible for focusing more on some desired issues. Artz, (2013, p. 337) states that both in developed and developing countries, following political and economic agendas in market-based- run private media is common today. Hegemony and political economy rely on consent and, consent leads to benefit. As agenda setting under terms and conditions of political entities give material benefits to media organization owner and workers. Therefore, whatever the actual reasons are, agenda setting is one of the most highly practised notions in news media which reconstructs public opinion by placing media salience over public agendas.

Similarly, Mccombs, (2011, p. 11) states that initially, the salience of an issue in mass media is directly linked to the formation of public opinion. As salience increases, neutrality among public decreases and, it leads to the formation of opinion according to the media agenda. Political agenda is said to be more prioritized on mass media as, (Aelst & Walgrave, 2016) more studies have systematically scrutinized how media contain political agenda. Within the domain of media research, it is hence, verified that political interest and media agenda-setting work hand in hand. In Pakistan there are a number of private media organizations are working. Almost all of them are correlated with both the entertainment and news industry. Statistics in 2019 found that more than 32 television news channels are operating and out of them only one is under the state's ownership and the rest are privately owned news media organizations. Naseer et al., (2018, p. 9) see Pakistani news media as potentially well capable of performing their all requisite duties. Despite facing many challenges, our media are keeping pace with the modern world. By airing diverse content, media reflect public opinion and inform them and also strengthen democracy. Yousafzai (2010) stated that news media in Pakistan play a very significant role, they have expanded the level of awareness regarding different issues, help to promote educational programs, provide support to public issues and have also, supported democracy. Rahman, (2014) states that news media are well capable of revealing the strength and weakness of governments and stop them to misuse power or to hide their misgovernance. They can also gather and promote public opinions to bring reformations in society. Currently, in Pakistan, there are a number of public affairs that need serious consideration. Besides, political matters, it is requisite to give thoughtful consideration to the quick fix of these issues. Shaikh & Nabi, (2017) state that, water and sanitation, poor housing schemes, education, health, transportation and, land management are the challenges that are required to be settled first. However, news media, on the other hand, tend to give more focus on political issues. Yousaf, (2017), in his article, scrawls it is not that our Pakistani media do not give coverage to basic issues rather, they are not much given due relevance that they should have. But, it is notable that media in developed countries, ensure a balance between political concerns and issues of civil emphasis. Remuneration is said to be the main discernment behind agenda-setting function on mass media.

Cardenas et al., (2017, p. 7) stated that exploring different factors affecting media development, it is suggested that quality of public interest based media reports are directly influenced by supply

and demand factors that, directly affect the production, representation and, dissemination of news. Saroshishar, (2016) expressed that framing is an effective way to represent political events and issues. For example, in electricity load shedding case, the matter is presented in the frames of bad governance, lack of resources, growing population to persuade them to increment their voice against injustice. The message replaces public agendas with political agendas. Therefore, whatever the reason is, the agenda-setting in news media is fundamental. This study will probe this phenomenon in a more systematic and empirical manner and, results will be generalizable in this regard. Hence, objectives of this study involve: To analyse the extent to which private news channels tend to emphasize more on political news as compared to other public/social issues in Pakistan. Therefore, the current study will address the following research question:

R1: Whether and to what extent preference is given to political topics over public interests in news media in Pakistan?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW:

There is an abundance of studies that affirm the agenda-setting role of mass media. These studies comprehensively discuss the role of mass media as a tool to prioritize the political agendas of government and other political entities over public agendas by influencing public opinion in a particular manner. Here is a summary of some studies that are addressing this issue in an embellished manner: Media in any form follow distant tactics to set public priorities according to their own agendas. To investigate this phenomenon Feezell, (2017) conducted a study that how public opinions can be altered by using social media. This study was based on the longitudinal method and, results revealed that the group of individuals who were shown political information on Facebook exhibited salient concern as compared to those who were not shown any political report. Agenda- setting in mass media has always been a debatable topic. Several investigations are made and diverse outcomes are documented. Luo et al., (2018) attempted to scrutinize agenda-setting studies from 1972 to 2015. In their investigation, they found that there is an apparent inconsistency in results across agenda-setting research studies and the existence of strong news media's public agenda-setting effects. Framing is a common practice in the media agenda setting. Drawing attention towards certain issues is highly being practice in mass media all around the world. A study conducted by Darcy & Cheng, (2017) investigated the agenda-setting the role of news media regarding ongoing development in draft Sydney Royal Botanic Gardens and Domain Trust Master Plan. Findings of their study revealed that exposure to this matter on news media has drawn the public's attention towards this matter as agenda setting and framing are the core background of news media proceedings in Australia.

New media have comparatively stronger and stable influences on public's perceptions as Teter, (2018) in her study named "Agenda-setting theory and the new media" investigated that does new media have any effects on public opinion to make it weaker or stronger?". Results revealed that the voice of new media in the media sphere is quite strong and, media agenda setting has quite a strong relation with shaping public opinion.

Aruguete, (2016) in her study "The agenda-setting hypothesis in the new media environment" scrutinized how new media has drastically changed patterns of agenda setting of traditional media. The researcher found that new media has altered their way agenda setting is being followed on traditional media forms. Media tend to prioritize agendas of political elites and, those entities which possess more power. Therefore, social media have introduced new trends of agenda-setting and ever growing users are being largely influenced by them. Today, people are being comparatively less exposed to traditional media forms. However, television and newspapers are still being considered as authentic information sources but, if they make combined efforts along with social media, agenda setting can become subtle and influential. Pierre & Shehata, (2017) postulated that the agenda-setting role of traditional media have media become weaker. They analysed individual and collective agenda setting effects on public opinion. Investigators found that there is very less evidence found regarding decreasing agenda-setting influence of traditional media rather, it is found that people get influenced more rapidly if, they are being exposed to agenda-setting function of both traditional and new media. Agenda- setting in mass media follows certain techniques of priming and framing. Issues are given attention and then a limited frame is utilized to build perceptions as, Scheufele & Tewkbury, (2017) in their article named "Framing, Agenda Setting, and Priming: The Evolution of Three Media Effects Models" explored how these three models are interrelated and what are their potential effects anticipated by theorists? They revealed that focus on some certain content occurs when, content is presented inside a frame and thus, draws the audience's attention. Partiality in mass media is a common tradition now a day. It is observable that every media organization has its own political opinion. Jan, Raza, Siddique & Saleem, (2013) to explore this matter, analysed coverage of political parties in two leading newspapers. They found that Daily News is giving comparatively more coverage to Pakistan Tehreek e Insaaf whereas, the Dawn is moderately covering respective political party as it remained neutral most of the time and reporting is concise and subjective. Mass media are well capable of setting certain priorities on public agenda. Bringing issues on the foreground and raising required perceptions is highly being practised in media. Riaz, (2018) analysed the relationship between public and print media agendas in Pakistan. A strong relationship was found between two stated variables except for the obtrusive issues. It was found that individuals' personal agendas were not relying on the media's agenda. However, it is suggested that the agenda-setting hypothesis should also include the obtrusive issue in its concern.

Shah et al., (2016) examined the correlation between print media's agendas and public agendas on national issues during general elections in 2013 in Pakistan. They found that there is a moderate correlation between the media agenda and the public agenda. Thus, this study had a strict policy and strategic implications. Newspaper reading is slightly declining in Pakistan as, information is easily accessible on social media and other information sources but, still print media practice agenda setting to build public perceptions. Mass media are well capable of portraying certain issues in an effective manner to spread awareness and solutions to respective problems. To scrutinize this matter Martin, (1992) conducted a follow-up investigation of Chapel hill study (1968). Their study concluded that mass media develops a mutual consensus of the public on some particular issue. Also, media public agendas gain attention and solution of issues if, public mutually agree on a workable solution to all the problems. Mass media are largely controlled by conglomerates and ruling political bodies. However, in many critical situations, the media follow the agendas of government and other ruling bodies

3. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK:

The field of mass communication contains a pile of theories that support and render the dynamics and, agendas of mass media proceedings. One such concept which supports this investigation is Agenda Setting theory. According to McCombs, (2011, p. 7), Agenda Setting theory tends to expand the understanding of the association between pictures in our minds and, the world outside. Maxwell McCombs hypothesized three major assumptions regarding the agenda-setting role of mass media. Gatekeeping, Priming and, Framing are the main propositions of this theoretical background. Altering public viewpoint through media agendas is the most rampant practice according to Agenda Setting theory. When some political action is brought on mass media (Alonso, 2014, p. 20) according to media laws, if it reaches to the desired target audience it surely leads to the higher public interest. In this case, political parties have to cooperate with journalists and the media to gain more consideration and, coverage. This collaboration with journalists is called Media Salacity which helps the public to believe the media agenda as prevailing and thought to provoke issue.

4. METHODOLOGY

In this quantitative study, the researchers used latent coding technique of content analysis technique for data collection procedure. Haggarty, (1996, p. 1) stated that content analysis is a method which assists a researcher to obtain and manipulate data in a systematic and reliable manner so that generalization can be made. Researcher assigned values (1=yes, 2=no) to gathered responses to manipulate the data and to obtain the results. Further, population of this study is comprised of all the electronic media news channels that are currently working in Pakistan and the sample is selected by using stratified sampling method in which, researcher first divided media channels into sub-groups and then selected the news channels from these groups relying, mainly upon popularity and ratings of respective news channels. Data is gathered from January 5th, 2019 to January 10, 2019 during 9 p.m. news bulletin.

Table 1: Sample of selected news media channels taken under consideration

News Channels	Launched	Language	Ownership
Geo News	2005	Urdu	Independent Media Organization
ARY News	2004	Urdu	ARY Group
Express News	2008	Urdu	Television Media Network
SAMAA TV	2007	Urdu	Jaag Broadcasting Systems (Pvt)
BOL Network	2013	Urdu	Shoaib Ahmed Shaikh

4.1 Validity & Unit of Analysis:

The drafted coding sheet was presented to the project supervisor for revision and approval before bringing it for the data collecting procedure. For data analysis process, Statistical Package for

Social Sciences (SPSS) is used. The cross-tabulation method is utilized to compute frequencies of responses and, the Chi-Square test is used to analyse the relationship between stated variables.

5. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The researcher first examined the extent to which coverage is given to respective news broadcast on selected channels as figure 2 shows the frequency and percentage of these reports. In this regard, Bol News is leading the coverage by broadcasting n=30 or 24.7% reports. Followed by ARY News (n=27 or 22.3%), both Geo News and Express-News broadcasted n=24 or 19.8% news reports. However, SAMAA News broadcasted comparatively, the lowest number of news (n=16n or 13.2%). Therefore, total frequency of news reports on all the selected news channels is 121 or 100%.

Similarly, after manipulation of gathered data, Cross-tabulation method is utilized to scrutinize the frequencies and a cumulative percentage of responses is also given in the below-mentioned table. Therefore, table 3 shows that political agendas as compared to public issues are given more focus on private news channels in Pakistan. News bulletins lacking a significant number of public issues, participation and welfare witness that how news media is being run by political elites and ruling body. In the descriptive analysis our preliminary research question “Whether and to what extent preference is given to political agendas over public interests in news media in Pakistan?” is comprehensively addressed by using content analysis technique and it is therefore, affirmed that news media in Pakistan tend to focus more on political issues than public issues. Results of our study have shown that news channels in Pakistan highly aim political issues as according to Aelst & Walgrave, (2016) political elites adopt media coverage for their personal interests. Media obtain information from governing political sources. First media obtain information and then, represent this erudition in a way that people start preferring this information over their own personal agendas. In this regard, the researcher scrutinized news coverage by stating seven distant variables indicating both public and political agendas. Disparate findings have unveiled that issues of a common man are given less focus as compared to political issues as it is revealed that general political news covered a larger part of news bulletin (n=58 or 47.5%) that were covering issues like corruption, the current government, press conferences of political leaders and current affair analyses. Similarly, national political news covers almost a major part of all the news coverages (n=101 or 86.1%) which were highlighting the ruling political body and other political parties in Pakistan. Further, it was found that despite mass media have a liability to encourage political participation to strengthen the trust of the common man on the democratic environment, only n=10 or 8.2% news reports were found lacking public participation. Ashraf, (2017) addressed these issues in a very delicate manner as he stated that media in Pakistan lack social responsibility. Like the political polarisation, our mass media are also divided into various categories highlighting and supporting agendas of political elites. Consequently, truth and public welfare have become merely a vague concept regarding media ethics.

Similarly, results also showed that political agendas were also given more preference over public agendas as only n=36 Or 29.5% news reports were covering issues of the common man despite the fact that public in Pakistan is facing a number of problems. Inflation, unemployment, declining

economic condition, health, education etc. all are problems which we are mainly facing today (Raza, 2018). However, there were very less number of news (n=134 or 10.7%) reports found that were explicitly supporting the current government and criticizing former governments but on the other hand, reports (n=36 or 29.5%) covering law and order situations, covering court hearings of former political leaders, discussing allegations and remarks of judges as an indispensable part of almost all the news bulletins on the selected news channels. Therefore, television news channels in Pakistan are clearly found lacking a sense of responsibility to support common man rights which is a thought-provoking phenomenon for mass media practitioners today.

Thus, Agenda setting is one of the most prominent concept of mass media which highlights how political agendas are given preference over public agendas in media. This study has proved the basic postulations of respective theory as it is observed that how certain political news are put forth, how these news reports are given excessive exposure and thus, how they are framed by media professionals so that general public can perceive them in a particular manner. According to Mahar, (2018) common man in Pakistan is facing a number of critical issues. Education, food, residence, law and justice hence, there are a number of other primary issues that are invading our lives every day. In such situation, where the common man is lacking basic necessities of life and human rights violation is occurring almost every day, being an integral part of a democratic system and their pertinence to raise awareness and solution of social problems, media should recognize their social responsibility. Giving an excessive exposure to political issues might be helpful and supportive for political bodies but sufferings of the common man still stay same as according to Saroshisar, (2016), agenda setting is one of the most preferred ways in Pakistani media to bring a matter in public's attention by creating certain way of thinking in their minds which may urge people to raise their voices but also abandon; the other basic issues. Therefore, this study has judiciously proved the agenda-setting role of Pakistani electronic media which affirms the statement "Political Agendas Over Public Interests".

6. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:

Media play an imperative role in altering public convictions as Matthes (2016, p. 17) states that people always get exposed to news media frames which results in enlightening or revamping public opinions. Their opinions are purely based on political information conveyed to them. It greatly influences contemporary democracies otherwise, a democratic environment cannot attain its actual goal and, for transferring political agenda on public agenda, media know how to create or change public opinion as Scirini, (2018, p. 1) states many studies have strongly authenticated the agenda-setting role of mass media. Issues priorities of policymakers are highly affected by agenda setting and thus, it leads to alteration of public opinion according to certain political agendas. While data gathering researcher found that national political reports covered the major part of bulletins on all selected news channels. News covering court hearings of former political leaders were being given more eminence while political statements and reports related to other political matters were also a major part of news announcements. Khokar, (p. 9) sees this role of television news media as setting up the gravity of certain political issues in people's minds. Therefore, media today are well capable of diverting our attention to "mediatized important"

issues. Malik, (2018) states that today, the common man in Pakistan is facing a number of issues. These may involve inflation, illiteracy, deficit, safety, accommodation, poor health facilities, lack of basic rights and many others. Yousaf, (2017) considers the role of Pakistani media as less focused on public issues. Floods, terrorism and other basic issues are not being given enough coverage. Private news media now rely on "readymade" news stuff as they primarily focus on reports that can give them the required attention and ratings. This means, media in Pakistan have abdicated from its core responsibility and public welfare is not their concern anymore. However, it is notable that the role of media is of greater pertinence. Being the fourth pillar of a democratic state. media is highly liable to highlight every existing complication in a country. According to Jamil, (2019), it is the media's responsibility to guide the people. But have we thought about the media's agenda-setting role for commercial interest? The truth is that the media have also become a victim as consumer culture and financial gain are now their main concern today. Less exposure to public interest and welfare based reports, it is found that news channels tend to give less attention to public issues but this does not underestimate the positive role of media. Happer & Phillo, (2013) see the positive role of media regarding bringing social changes. According to the media can help people to alter their minds and bring positivism through their collective efforts and, for this purpose media have to dominate their convictions and belief systems. In Pakistan, news media should be impartial to change the convictions and reinforce positive constructive thinking among the public. Sensitivity towards public issues should also be sizable for news media. Brewer, (2018) stated that being impartial does not mean leaving own beliefs and opinions. Every media organization and journalists have their own interests and convictions but for public welfare, they must rise above their own perceptions and opinions and, by keeping interests of common man media organizations can fulfil their obligations. Media institution has played a fundamental role in bringing socio-political reforms in Pakistan. Its coverage on human rights and crime issues testifies agony of the common man in our society. Somehow, in the name of immunity of expression, Pakistani media today focus more on ratings and fierce competition which undermine legitimate and impartial reporting and it leads media channels to adopt unethical and tendentious media practices (Daffy, 2016, p. 4). Therefore, besides political agendas, news media in Pakistan should also give sufficient attention to concerns of the common man as, public participation and welfare are considered to be the main aphorism of journalism and media practice worldwide.

5.1 Limitations of the Study:

Due to limited timeframe, financial resources and other related constraints this study is conducted on a small scale however, all the quintessential techniques are used to obtain and calculate the data. Furthermore, the researchers have cautiously analysed the gathered data and results are presented in an appropriate manner. Here researcher suggests more inquiries regarding the agenda-setting role of mass media under the conceptual framework conducted by Prof Maxwell McCombs and Donald Shaw. Although this study succinctly illustrates how under the respective notion of agenda setting television news channels in Pakistan are prioritizing political concerns over public interests, we still need to scrutinize these phenomena in a more comprehensive manner so that, other relevant facets of the agenda-setting role of mass media could be explored.

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